

Feedback Form

This form aims to understand your perceptions regarding the anti-patterns catalog in micro frontend-oriented architectures.

Section 1/4

1. What's your full name?

Section 2/4 - Anti-patterns Catalog Evaluation

Please answer the questions below using a scale from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree" regarding your understanding of Micro Frontends (MFEs), as well as the usefulness, ease of use, and intention to use the Anti-patterns catalog for MFEs in the future.

1. Catalog's utility
 - a. Using the anti-patterns catalog for MFEs improves my performance when developing MFE-oriented architectures.
 - b. Using the anti-patterns catalog for MFEs improves my productivity when developing MFE-oriented architectures.
 - c. Using the anti-patterns catalog for MFEs improves my effectiveness in communicating with other developers when working on MFE-oriented architectures.
 - d. I consider the anti-patterns catalog for MFEs useful for developing MFE-oriented architectures.
2. Did you **use** or **not use** the anti-patterns catalog for MFEs during the evaluation exercise? If yes, how did you use it? If not, why didn't you use it?
3. Ease of use of the catalog
 - a. My interaction with the MFE anti-patterns catalog was clear and understandable.
 - b. Interacting with the MFE anti-patterns catalog did not require much mental effort.
 - c. I consider the MFE anti-patterns catalog easy to use.
 - d. I find it easy to use the MFE anti-patterns catalog during the development of MFE-oriented architectures.
4. Did you notice any benefits or challenges when using the MFE anti-patterns catalog? Any ease or difficulty of use? If so, which ones?
5. Intention to use the catalog in the future
 - a. Assuming I have enough time to design and develop an MFE-oriented architecture, I would use the MFE anti-patterns catalog.
 - b. Considering that I could choose other tools to support the development of MFE-oriented architectures, I intend to use the MFE anti-patterns catalog.

- c. I intend to use the MFE anti-patterns catalog the next time I work on an MFE-oriented architecture.

Section 3/4 - Learning

Answer the questions below on a scale from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree” regarding your learning about Micro Frontends (MFEs) using the MFE Anti-patterns Catalog.

1. Consider the following statements about your learning of MFE-oriented architectures:
 - a. I consider that having access to the MFE anti-patterns catalog was relevant to my learning.
 - b. I find it easy to use the MFE anti-patterns catalog to learn about MFE-oriented architectures.
 - c. The MFE anti-patterns catalog made it easier to learn about best practices in software architecture.
 - d. The MFE anti-patterns catalog contributed to my understanding of common pitfalls in MFE architectures.
2. Please describe here whether and how the MFE anti-patterns catalog **helped** or **hindered** your learning about Micro Frontends.

Section 4/4 - General Feedback

Finally, please answer the following questions about your experience with the Micro Frontends Anti-patterns Catalog.

1. Rate your perceived knowledge about micro frontends from 0 to 5 after using the catalog.
2. Do you have any suggestions for improving the catalog? If you had difficulty understanding the definition of any anti-pattern (considering the fields for problem, solution, and example), please indicate which anti-pattern it was and describe what was unclear.